

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Mineral Acid catalysed Hydrolysis of *N*-Methylbenzohydroxamic Acid

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Hydroxamic acids and their derivatives have been the subject of numerous investigations because of their importance in biological, analytical and medicinal fields¹. We have studied the acidic hydrolysis of unsubstituted (BHA)^{2a}, phenylsubstituted (PBHA)^{2b} and benzyl substituted (BBHA)^{2c} hydroxamic acids. However, the hydrolysis of methyl substituted (MBHA) hydroxamic acids have received scanty attention. The previous study of acidic hydrolysis of some *ortho*-substituted *N*-methylbenzohydroxamic acids³ covered the low acidity range (0.149–0.751 *M* HCl) where the information gained about detailed mechanism is limited. We have therefore undertaken hydrolysis of *N*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid (C₆H₅·(C=O)·N(OH)·CH₃) in HCl, H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ solutions in 20% (v/v) dioxane. Attempts have also been made to correlate the relative influence of the group on the nitrogen end of the hydroxamic acid moiety, and the contributions of electronic effects.

Results and Discussion

Rate dependence on acidity : The acidic hydrolysis of the *N*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid (MBHA) is of first order both in substrate and catalyst, viz acid, but as the hydrolysis was carried out in excess hydronium ion pseudo-first order rates were ensured. The rate of hydrolysis passes through a maximum in all the mineral acids (Table 1). This is attributed to two opposing effects of increasing the acid concentration. On the one hand increased acidity raises the concentration of the reactive conjugate acid form of the substrate, and at the same time activity of water needed for complete hydrolysis decreases. Such an explanation for the hydrolysis is supported by values of the kinetic solvent isotope effect (k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O}) which are 1.51 and 1.62 for the hydrolysis of MBHA in 2.9 *M* D₂SO₄ and DCl respectively. If we compare the rate of hydrolysis of various hydroxamic acids (Table 2) studied kinetically, the order is MBHA > BBHA > PBHA > BHA, in the acidity region in which the hydrolysis proceeds by the A-2 mechanism. MBHA has been observed to undergo hydrolysis by about 3 times faster than BHA (Table 2). The rate of hydrolysis of BBHA is fast compared to PBHA. It may be due to electron-donating nature of CH₂ group attached between C₆H₅ and the nitrogen of the functional group. This may facilitate the protonation of substrate. MBHA reacts faster. The methyl group on the N atom

plays the dominant role. Various resonance forms indicate the possible electron delocalisation for the substituted *N*-methylbenzohydroxamic anions. These resonance forms suggest that there is relatively little electron delocalisation with respect to the phenyl ring. The increased net molecular dipole for the MBHA results in a greater interaction with the solvent molecules.

TABLE 1—ACID CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF MBHA IN HCl, H₂SO₄ AND HClO₄

T_{emp.} = 55°, 20% (v/v) Dioxane (MBHA) = 4.96 × 10⁻³ *M*

<i>M</i>	k_{ψ} (10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)		
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	HClO ₄
0.75	0.68	0.571	0.88
1.75	1.55	1.52	1.41
2.00	—	1.85	—
2.90	2.50	2.55	1.50
2.90	3.78 ^a	4.13 ^b	—
3.22	—	—	1.56
3.50	2.70	2.49	1.75
4.22	3.20	2.55	1.59
5.00	3.08	2.00	1.41
5.80	3.26	1.23	1.08
6.50	3.00	0.761	0.73
7.50	2.15	—	0.38
8.50	1.82	—	0.16
9.00	1.40	—	—

^aDCl in D₂O. ^bD₂SO₄ in D₂O.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON AT 55° IN 2.9 *M* AND 20% (v/v) DIOXANE

Compd.	k_{ψ} (10 ⁵ s ⁻¹)		
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	HClO ₄
BHA	7.58	9.08	5.20
PBHA	9.58	10.4	5.64
BBHA	17.8	18.0	13.6
MBHA	25.0	25.5	15.0

Activation parameters : The values of activation parameters at different acidities are recorded in Table 3. These values are fairly typical for A-2 reactions⁴. The ΔH^{\ddagger} and ΔS^{\ddagger} values vary in a more or less compensating manner. Of more interest is the variation of ΔS^{\ddagger} with acid concentration, the ΔS^{\ddagger} changing from a larger negative value of around -74 to -108 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ in the more dilute acid

region, to less negative values around -64 to -81 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ in more concentrated regions. This implies that a change from a more to a less restricted transition state is occurring as the acidity is increased (as $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is decreased).

Rate acidity correlations: The rate data have been analysed by Bunnett-Olsen LFER⁵, Bunnett ω parameter⁶ and relatively recently introduced Cox-Yates⁷ excess acidity approaches. The data are first correlated by the Bunnett-Olsen linear free energy relationship (H_A is the amide acidity function),

$$\log k_{\psi} + H_A = \phi (H_A + \log [\text{H}^+]) + \text{constant} \quad (1)$$

Correlation of $\log k_{\psi} + H_A$ with $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (Bunnett ω) was also attempted. The ϕ values (Table 4) imply that water plays some additional role in the rate-determining step besides behaving as a nucleophile. The ω values suggest that water played the role of a proton transfer agent. On the basis of Bunnett⁶ treatment, which takes into account the difference in the degree of hydration of hydrated state and the reactants, we can say that the transition state is more polar.

Recently, the excess acidity method has been found to be very useful in obtaining information concerning a wide variety of reactions which takes place in mineral acids^{7,8}. In this method it is argued⁷ that an A-2 mechanism should obey equation (2). Here m^* is a parameter characteristic of the protonation of the substrate S , and m^\ddagger a parameter characteristic of the transition state. It is normally found that for A-1 mechanism, $m^* > 1$, and for A-2 mechanism, $m^* < 1$. The m^* for carbonyl protonation is 0.6 or less. Thus a total slope against X of 0.6 or less would be expected for equation (2),

$$\log k_{\psi} - \log [\text{H}^+] - \gamma \log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = m^* m^\ddagger X + \text{constant} \quad (2)$$

For measurements of k_{ψ} over a significant range of acidity (i.e. of X) a plot of $\log k_{\psi} - \log \text{H}^+ - \gamma \log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ against X should be a straight-line for an A-2 mechanism. Normally for A-AC₂ mechanism $\gamma \sim 2$. The slope values (Table 4) are consistent with the A-2 mechanism shown in Scheme 1.

TABLE 3—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF *N*-METHYLBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID IN DIFFERENT ACIDS

<i>M</i>	HCl				H ₂ SO ₄				HClO ₄			
	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	Corr. coeff	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	Corr. coeff	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	Corr. coeff
0.75	78.6	-87	104.3	0.998	82.8	-74	104.8	0.996	71.7	-108.0	103.6	0.960
2.9	73.6	-92	100.0	0.994	76.2	-83	100.8	0.999	73.2	-96	101.5	0.998
5.0	79.3	-72	100.5	0.999	76.8	-82	101.1	0.993	80.0	-75	102.3	0.996
6.5	79.3	-72	100.6	0.999	79.9	-81	104.0	0.999	85.6	-64	104.4	0.996

ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} , ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$

TABLE 4—RATE ACIDITY CORRELATIONS

	HCl			H ₂ SO ₄			HClO ₄		
	Acid range	Slope	Corr. coeff	Acid range	Slope	Corr. coeff	Acid range	Slope	Corr. coeff
Bunnett ω	2.9 - 7.50	5.81	0.998	2.00 - 6.5	5.61	0.999	1.75 - 5.00	6.55	0.991
Bunnett-Olsen	1.75 - 6.50	1.31	0.999	2.00 - 5.00	1.54	0.995	1.75 - 6.50	1.72	0.997
Excess acidity	0.75 - 6.50	0.154	0.995	0.75 - 4.22	0.187	0.999	6.5 - 8.5	0.116	0.972

Mechanistic pathway : The currently favoured A-2 mechanism for acid catalysed hydrolysis is depicted in Scheme 1. The carbonyl oxygen is protonated, the carbonyl carbon is attacked by H_2O , protons are transferred, and a methyl hydroxylamine is expelled. This amine then reacts with H^+ to yield the protonated methylhydroxylamine. There is no direct evidence available to indicate the site of protonation of hydroxamic acid. However, more data is needed for *N*-substituted-hydroxamic acids in order to make an assessment. Such effort is currently in progress. Our present results also indicate that there is no mechanism change in the acid catalysed hydrolysis upon introduction of an *N*-methyl groups in hydroxamic acids.

Experimental

N-Methylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by reaction of benzoyl chloride with *N*-methylhydroxylamine⁹. The acids used were of A.R. grade and dioxane (AnalaR) was used as such. Kinetic measurements were made by the spectrophotometric method^{2c}. Deuterium chloride (isotopic purity, > 95%), deuterium oxide (D_2O ; isotopic purity, > 99.8%) and D_2SO_4 (isotopic purity, > 95%) were procured from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay. Employing a Systronics 108 spectrophotometer set at 520 nm, the values of pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated for each run from the standard equation. Least-squares analyses were carried out on a WIPRO-SX-386 PC under MS-DOS.

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References

- (a) L. BAUER and O. LAMER, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1974, **12**, 376; (b) C. M. PICKART and W. P. HENCKS, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1970, **254**, 9120; (c) "Chemistry and Biology of Hydroxamic Acids", ed. H. KEHL, Karger, Basel, 1982, (d) M. FAMULOK, F. BOSOLD and G. BOCHE, *Angew. Chem.*, 1989, **101**, 349, (e) M. I. M. VANDEPOLL, M. V. M. LAFLEUR, F. VANGOG, H. VRIELING and J. H. N. MEERMAN, *Carcinogenesis*, 1992, **13**, 751, (f) S. SWAMINATHAN and C. A. REZNIKOFF, *Cancer Res.*, 1992, **52**, 3286; (g) M. NOVAK, M. J. KAHLEY, E. EIGER, J. S. HELMICK and H. E. PETERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 9453; (h) B. CHATTERJEE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1978, **26**, 281.
- (a) K. K. GHOSH, S. K. RAJPUT and K. K. KRISHNANI, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1992, **5**, 39; (b) K. K. GHOSH and S. GHOSH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1994, **59**, 1369; (c) K. K. GHOSH and S. G. TANDON, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, **62**, 1304.
- D. C. BERNDT and I. E. WARD, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1976, **41**, 3297.
- L. L. SCHALEGER and F. A. LONG, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 24.
- J. F. BUNNETT and F. P. OLSEN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 1899.
- J. F. BUNNETT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4956.
- R. A. COX, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1987, **20**, 27.
- (a) Y. BÉDEMÉR, J. G. TILLET and ZALEWSKI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1993, 1943; (b) V. B. JOSEPH and D. P. N. SATCHELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **2**, 339, (c) R. A. COX, I. ONYIDU and E. BUNCEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 1358.
- U. PRIYADARSHINI and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1967, **12**, 143.